

Measuring personality traits of professionals in a technology-driven library ecosystem

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Abstract:

The current study aims to investigate the extent to which personality and demographic variables contribute to professional development of library professionals in the present rapidly changing environment of information system. A total of 104 full time library professionals participated in the survey measuring their personality traits, demographic parameters and professional development skills. Results demonstrate that 25% of the variance in Context knowledge skill and 14% of the variance in Collections & discovery skill are accounted for by the Big Five personality traits and demographic variables. Openness to experience and Conscientiousness are significant predictors of both the skills Context knowledge and Collections & discovery. Negative relationship is found between Context knowledge and Neuroticism. Two demographic variables age and job status are significantly correlated to each other. Professionals with high score of Openness to experience and Conscientiousness are expected to excel in the skills Context knowledge, Personal skill and Collections & discovery, implying that they can keep up-to-date with the information technology used in library services in the present days. Our present study indicates whether a library professional is ready to implement latest information technology in library services by adapting himself, depends upon his different personality traits.

Keywords : BFPI, CAVAL competency, Five-Factor Model, FFA, ICT application, LIS professionals' psychology, personality test

1 Introduction

Academic libraries have been the integral and vital component of the education system which extends supports to education, learning, training and fulfilment of objectives and mission of the educational institutions they are part of. Being the 'heart of the university', repository of knowledge and gateways of information, higher academic libraries and librarians have to explore innovative ways to fulfill the information needs of the users specially keeping in view the paradigmatic shift in knowledge generation and management, constant invention of new web resources and presence of information search and retrieval tools. The rapid electronic dissemination of information, technological development and generational change force to change the concept of 21st century library services. Continuous professional development become an essential part to cope up with these technological changes.

2 Background of the study

Change, in organisations as elsewhere, involves moving from a known state to a new state – one that is to some degree unknown. Change involves letting go of things as they are in order to take up new ways of doing things (Smith, 2005).

Lois V. Green and Robert A. Clarke (1995) explained that the changes in the role of academic librarian have been variously attributed to: the enterprise culture, the new managerialism, economics, IT and educational changes. Change has been continual and far-reaching in libraries since the late 1980s. Automation of information systems has been the driving force behind transformations both in the library environment and in reference service practices (Walton, G. et al., 1996). The knowledge and skills that workers had acquired through education and on-the-job experience may no longer be relevant for jobs that have been redesigned. Therefore, the competence of librarians has become an even greater issue in the last few years. Professional librarians are motivated to maintain their professional competence but more can be done to encourage and facilitate their participation in updating activities (Chan & Auster, 2003).

Library and information science (LIS) is currently characterised by fast-paced change, with staff needing to be flexible in adapting and adopting new skills and levels of awareness (Ashcroft, 2004). Job satisfaction has been correlated with a variety of personality traits in psychology. Trait systems studied in relation to job satisfaction include the Big Five Personality Traits (Judge et al., 2002).

J. W. Lounsbury et al. (2003) studied a diverse sample of 5,932 individuals in fourteen separate occupational groups and found that job satisfaction was significantly related to Assertiveness, Conscientiousness, Customer Service Commitment, Emotional Stability, Extraversion, Openness to experience, Optimism, Tough-Mindedness, and Work Drive.

There is revolutionary changes in information handling activities throughout past few decades as a result of advancement in Information and Communication Technology (ICT). “The 21st century information professional must possess skills in selection, content management, knowledge management, organization of information on intranets and the Internet, research services, developing and maintaining digital libraries, and bringing information resources to the desktop. People with the right skills are crucial for success and competitiveness in contemporary information environments.” Varalakshmi (2006) predicted that the majority of jobs in libraries and information centers will be ICT-related in future.

Pamment Terri (2008) explored the role of professional development (PD) in assisting established and new LIS practitioners to update and extend their knowledge and skills. Although his study has identified that some employers require generic skills at a high level, a study comparing job advertisement requirements with the skills of successful applicants may give a truer of the current skills level of the 21st century LIS workers. It has been identified from various articles (Ahmed, Shamsad & Rasheed, Tariq, 2020; Cattell, 1943; George, 1992; Goldberg, Lewis R., 1990; Judge et al., 2002; Lounsbury et al., 2003; Lounsbury, John W et al., 2007; Pemberton, Anne E. et al., 2005; Seibert & Kraimer, 2001; Therasa & Vijayabanu, 2015) that studies on personality traits of librarians and other information professionals have been started since mid of 20th century, but until now, there has been no comprehensive effort to relate personality trait with professional development of LIS professionals in the changing environment.

So in the recent changing environment a relevant question arises whether a library professional will be able to adapt himself with new technologies (i.e, our aspirations) or he fails to provide information technology based services to the users (i.e., our apprehensions). This is actually related to his professional development in the changing work environment. This professional development depends upon many

factors such as motivation, job satisfaction, formal and informal updating activities, personality traits, etc. In this article we concentrate on how the psychology of an individual affects his professional development in the recent technology driven library eco-system.

3. **Related concepts and hypothesis**

Before entering into the main study few relevant concepts have been described in this section like Professional development, CAVAL Competencies for Academic and Research Librarians, Personality Traits and Big Five Personality Traits. In addition to that some predictions of this study have been made in this section.

Professional development

Professional development is learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, conferences and informal learning opportunities situated in practice. It has been described as intensive and collaborative, ideally incorporating an evaluative stage. (“Professional Development,” 2022) In education, the term professional development may be used in reference to a wide variety of specialized training, formal education, or advanced professional learning intended to help administrators, teachers and other educators improve their professional knowledge, competence, skill and effectiveness. (*Professional Development Definition*, 2013)

CAVAL Competencies for Academic and Research Librarians

These competencies are built on the “Core Competencies for 21st Century CARL Librarians”, October 2010. CAVAL is a “for benefit” member-based co-operative of ten Australian academic libraries, most of which are based in the state of Victoria. This publication provides an up to date overview of the competencies required for libraries to deliver excellent learning and teaching support to their university and research communities. Seven Core competencies for academic and research librarians have been described to identify knowledge, experience, skill, and attitudinal areas where there is potential for improvement through organisational, team and individual training and professional development. (*CAVAL_PDIG_Competencies_2017.Pdf*, n.d.)

Personality Trait

The term "personality trait" refers to enduring personal characteristics that are revealed in a particular pattern of behaviour in a variety of situations. (*Personality Definition - English Dictionary | Personality Explanations and Pronunciations*, n.d.) J. Block (1995) mentioned in his article that “the 5-factor approach (FFA) to personality description has been represented as a comprehensive and compelling rubric for assessment.” He also outlined various misgivings about the FFA.

Big Five Personality Traits

The Big Five personality traits, also known as the five factor model (FFM), is a model based on common language descriptors of personality (lexical hypothesis). These descriptors are grouped together using a statistical technique called factor analysis (i.e. this model is not based on experiments). This widely examined theory suggests five broad dimensions used by some psychologists to describe the human personality and psyche. The five factors have been defined as Openness to experience (O), Conscientiousness (C), Extraversion (E), Agreeableness (A), and Neuroticism (N), often listed under the acronyms *OCEAN* or *CANOE* (“Big Five Personality Traits,” 2022).

In this technology-driven library ecosystem “librarian should be more competent and remain flexible for the future technological development to cope up with the ever changing environment” (Mandal & Dasgupta, 2019). Based on previous research and speculative observations, the following predictions can be made:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): There should be significant relationship between CAVAL competency skills of library professionals and Big Five personality traits.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): It is expected that when CAVAL competency skill is regressed onto Big Five personality traits, personality variables will account for a significant proportion of the variance.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Conscientiousness will be positively, and neuroticism will be negatively correlated with the competency skill Context knowledge.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): There will be a significant relationship between age and job status.

4. Methodology

4.1 **Participants:** In all, 104 full time employees (73 males, mean age = 42.2 years, standard deviation = 9.42, and 31 females, mean age = 38.4 years, standard deviation = 7.70) took part in this survey. They are employed in the libraries or information centres of higher academic and research institutions of West Bengal.

4.2 **Instruments:** The Big Five Personality Inventory (BFPI-SAKA), designed by National Psychological Corporation, consists of 180 items. This inventory was used to measure quantitatively the five dimensions of personality traits, namely Openness to experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness and Neuroticism .

To characterise the professional development of library professionals we take help of the standard “CAVAL Competencies for Academic and Research Librarians, November 2017”. In this standard competency there are seven skills to characterise the professional development. In the present article we consider only 3 skills, namely Context knowledge, Personal skills and Collections & discovery. Because the items corresponding to each skill are mostly related to library services with the help of information technologies which are discussed in the following sections. “Survey monkey” tool has been used to design an online questionnaire to quantify the above mentioned professional skills.

4.3 **Procedure:** Participants were communicated through group e-mail which outlined the purpose of the questionnaire. Participation was anonymous and participants were requested to complete the questionnaire through an online survey link.

4.3.1 **Dependent variables:**

In our survey the dependent variables are the three CAVAL competency skills i.e., Context knowledge, Personal skill and Collections & discovery. The following sections discuss the measurement of the variables.

4.3.1.1 **Context Knowledge:** We treat Context knowledge as one of the measures of professional development of library professionals. It comprises of two items – a. Keeping up-to-date in LIS recent development and b. DSpace awareness. On each item relevant questions are designed and responses are collected on a seven-point scale. The points corresponding to all items are summed to create an overall score for the skill Context knowledge.

4.3.1.2 Personal skill: This professional development skill consists of seven items which are as follows:

- a. Discussion with colleagues
- b. Entirely new job responsibility
- c. Continuous Professional Development (CPD) activity
- d. Use of Datawrangling tool
- e. Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) service
- f. Application of web 3.0
- g. Flexibility for new experience and knowledge in LIS

Relevant questions are set corresponding to each item and responses are collected on a seven-point scale. Then the points corresponding to all items are summed to create an overall score for the Personal skill factor.

4.3.1.3 Collections & discovery: This skill consists of six parameters which are mentioned below:

- a. Maintaining institutional repository
- b. Following digitization process
- c. Measuring usage statistics
- d. Consulting Union catalogue
- e. Discovery system (VuFind)
- f. Library Management Software related activity (Koha)

Like the earlier method we create an overall score corresponding to the professional development skill Collections & discovery.

4.3.2 Independent variables:

We consider the standard Big Five personality traits i.e., Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness and Neuroticism, as our independent variables. We also consider two demographic variables namely, 'Age' and 'Job status' as independent variables in addition to these five variables. Here we consider the designation of each library professional as Job status. We quantify the variable job status by grading the corresponding designation on a seven-point scale.

5 Results

In our study we investigate the correlation between the five personality trait variables and the three skills of professional development variables characterised by the CAVAL competency skills.

5.1 Correlational analysis

Table 1 [*Intercorrelations of all variables*] illustrates the intercorrelations among the five personality traits, 3 CAVAL competency skills, age & job status. Context knowledge is negatively correlated with Neuroticism ($p < 0.05$). The competency skills Context knowledge and Collections & discovery are positively correlated with Openness to experience (both $p < 0.01$) and Personal skill is positively correlated with Openness to experience ($p < 0.05$). Similarly context knowledge and Collections & discovery are positively correlated with Conscientiousness (both $p < 0.01$). Personal skill is also positively correlated with Conscientiousness ($p < 0.05$). Age is positively correlated with Conscientiousness ($p < 0.05$). Job status is positively correlated with Conscientiousness ($p < 0.05$). We see that age and job status are highly correlated to each other ($p < 0.01$). In our survey we find that the competency skill Collections & discovery is positively correlated with Context knowledge ($p < 0.05$) and Personal skill ($p < 0.01$). Neuroticism is negatively correlated with Extraversion and Agreeableness (both $p < 0.01$). It is also negatively correlated with Conscientiousness ($p < 0.05$). Our data show the significant positive correlation between Extraversion and Agreeableness ($p < 0.01$).

Table 1: Intercorrelations of all variables

Variables	Correlations								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Context Knowledge	-								
2 Personal Skill	0.11	-							
3 Collections and discovery	0.22 *	0.75 **	-						
4 Neuroticism	-0.17 *	-0.05	0	-					
5 Extraversion	0.04	0.02	0.06	-0.34 **	-				
6 Openness to experience	0.29 **	0.16 *	0.24 **	0.07	0.04	-			
7 Agreeableness	0.05	0.06	0	-0.25 **	0.41 **	0.08	-		
8 Conscientiousness	0.41 **	0.21 *	0.26 **	-0.15 *	0	0.08	0.06	-	
9 Age	0.11	0.01	-0.04	-0.08	-0.06	0.03	-0.05	0.16 *	-
10 Job status	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.17	-0.2	0.06	-0.13	0.19 *	0.40 **

Notes: N = 104; * Correlations are significant at $p < 0.05$; ** Correlations are significant at $p < 0.01$

5.2 Regression analysis

In order to investigate the impact of individual differences upon professional development parameters three regressions are performed, with the three professional development scores regressed onto the Big five personality traits, age and job status. Two out of three regressions are shown to be significant (one at $p < 0.01$ and the other at $p < 0.05$), and the output is illustrated in Table 2 [*Regressions of Context Knowledge, Personal skill and Collection & discovery onto personality, age and job status*] in compact form. Results demonstrate that the independent variables accounted for 25% of the variance for the CAVAL competency skill Context knowledge variable ($F(7, 96) = 4.60, p < 0.01$). Both personality traits Openness to experience and Conscientiousness are significant positive predictors in the equation (both $p < 0.01$).

Table 2: Regressions of Context Knowledge, Personal skill and Collections & discovery onto personality, age and job status						
	Context Knowledge F (7, 96) = 4.60** R ² = 0.25		Personal Skill F (7, 96) = 1.04 R ² = 0.07		Collections & discovery F (7, 96) = 2.18* R ² = 0.14	
	β	t	β	t	β	t
Neuroticism	-0.14	-1.43	-0.04	-0.37	0.01	0.09
Extraversion	-0.01	-0.06	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.91
Openness to experience	0.27	3.00**	0.14	1.4	0.21	2.22*
Agreeableness	-0.02	-0.24	0.03	0.26	-0.07	-0.62
Conscientiousness	0.36	3.92**	0.18	1.77	0.25	2.47*
Age	0.03	0.29	-0.06	-0.57	-0.13	-1.19
Job status	0.01	0.06	0.08	0.73	0.11	1.02

*Notes: N = 104; *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01*

Regression of Collections & discovery skill reveals that the predictor variables accounted for 14% of the variance in the Collection & discovery factor (F (7, 96) = 2.18, p<0.05). Out of the five personality variables, Openness to experience and Conscientiousness are found to be statistically significant predictors of this skill (both p<0.05). The output reveals that other personality variables, age and job status do not significantly contribute to the regression equation (all p>0.05). In our regression analysis of the competency variable Personal skill we find that no independent variable is statistically significant predictor of the Personal skill variable in the regression equation (all p>0.05)

6 Discussions

The present study is intended to investigate the extent to which personality, age and job status explain variance in three professional development skills, namely Context knowledge, Personal skill and Collections & discovery. Earlier different library services were mostly manual, but gradually different services have been changed from manual to digital mode. In the present survey we also look for how library professionals have adapted themselves in providing the digital based services to the users in the current rapidly changing environment.

As expected the personality trait Openness to experience is significant positive correlate of the skills Context knowledge, Personal skill and Collections & discovery. We know that Openness to experience indicates general appreciation for art, emotion, adventure, unusual ideas, imagination, curiosity and variety of experience. People who are open to experience are intellectually curious, open to emotion and willing to try new things. People who have openness to experience have tendency to acquire knowledge of various things which is reflected in our study by the positive correlation of Openness to experience with Context knowledge.

Positive correlation of Openness to experience with Personal skill implies that library professionals are ready for lifelong learning for their development, willing to provide useful advice to other professionals to attain success in their field, ready to take initiative for new library service and prefer to involve them in social and web-based technologies.

People with high score in Openness to experience have the capability of managing the electronic resources and are ready to be part of digitization process with emphasis on institutional repository which is reflected in our study by the positive correlation of Collection & discovery with Openness to experience.

High Conscientiousness is often perceived as being stubborn, focused, efficient and organised. An efficient and focussed individual is expected to excel in all the three CAVAL competency skills which is reflected in our study by the positive significant correlation of Conscientiousness with all the three skills. This result means that professionals are well acquainted with the library system as well as institutional objectives and goals. They are flexible and eager for new experience and knowledge in LIS. All these results support our first hypothesis *H1* that there should be significant relationship between competency skills of library professionals and their personality traits.

Negative significant relationship is observed between Context knowledge and Neuroticism. We can understand it by the fact that high score Neuroticism means nervousness, sensitiveness, more emotional, depressed which ultimately negatively affects a library professional to have Context knowledge. As per our consideration for this study Context knowledge indicates overall knowledge of library system with which library professionals work, their knowledge about scholarly communication models & practices and legal issues related to the academic library environment. This

negative behaviour is consistent with our hypothesis *H3* that Neuroticism is negatively correlated with the competency skill Context knowledge.

In our survey we find that personality and demographic variables are significant correlates of the skill Context knowledge, accounting for 25% of the variance. Similarly personality and demographic variables are also significantly related to the competency skill Collections & discovery and accounted for 14% of the variance. This result supports our second hypothesis *H2* that when CAVAL competency skill is regressed onto Big Five personality traits, personality variables will account for a significant proportion of the variance.

Our data reveal that two demographic variables age and job status are significantly correlated to each other. This is justified by the fact that as the age of a library professional increases they are promoted to higher post with their professional knowledge and experience implying higher job status. This confirms our prediction *H4* that there will be a significant relationship between age and job status.

Positive relationship is observed between the demographic variable age and the personality trait Conscientiousness. This is also expected that with the increase of age a library professional becomes more organised (i.e., high score in Conscientiousness). The positive correlation between job status and the Conscientiousness is easily understandable by the fact that organised, focused, dutiful and target oriented library professionals (i.e., high score in Conscientiousness) is expected to have a higher job status.

Interestingly the professional skill Collections & discovery is significantly related to Context knowledge and Personal skill which is justified by the observation that the library professionals with good Context knowledge and Personal skill are expected to have better knowledge in collection development, electronic resource management, Integrated Library System (ILS), digitization process and preservation.

In our survey we also find that there is negative relationship of Neuroticism with personality traits Extraversion, Agreeableness and Conscientiousness. It implies that a professional who has tendency to be nervous, tensed, anxious and depressed is expected to have low score in Extraversion, Agreeableness and Conscientiousness.

Our survey shows significant positive relationship between Extraversion and Agreeableness which implies that a library professional who is more energetic, positive emotional, assertive in nature (i.e., having high score in Extraversion) is

expected to have tendency to be compassionate and cooperative rather than suspicious and antagonistic towards others (i.e., high score in Agreeableness).

7 Limitation and direction for future studies

We acknowledge a few limitations of the current study. Firstly, we have considered only three CAVAL competency skills. Secondly, our survey is restricted in the higher academic and research institutions of West Bengal only. Thirdly, gender has not been considered as independent variable. These limitations of current research may be addressed in future studies.

8 Conclusion

For information professionals, maintaining competence is of vital importance in the continuously changing work environment in the 21st century. Library profession has been experiencing rapid technological change with the development of information technologies. Individual having positive relationship among their competency skills is expected to form a healthy institution and healthy work environment. Whether a library professional is able to cope up with the changing library services with the introduction of different information technologies (i.e, his professional development) depends upon his different personality traits. The present survey demonstrates that personality and demographic variables are significantly related to various professional development factors as defined by standard CAVAL competency skills.

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